

Article

Experimental Interference Robustness Evaluation of IEEE 802.15.4-2015 OQPSK-DSSS and SUN-OFDM Physical Layers for Industrial Communications

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Abstract: In this paper we experimentally evaluate and compare the robustness against interference of the OQPSK-DSSS (Offset Quadrature Phase Shift Keying - Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum) and the SUN-OFDM (Smart Utility Network - Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing) physical layers, as defined in the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 standard. The objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the impact that different levels of interference produce on these modulations, in terms of the resulting PDR (Packet Delivery Ratio) and depending on the length of the packet being transmitted. The results show that the SUN-OFDM physical layer provides significant benefits compared to the ubiquitous OQPSK-DSSS in terms of interference robustness, regardless of the interference type and the packet length. Overall, this demonstrates the suitability of choosing the SUN-OFDM physical layer when deploying low-power wireless networks in industrial scenarios, specially taking into consideration the possibility of trading-off robustness and spectrum efficiency depending on the application requirements.

Keywords: IEEE 802.15.4; Smart Utility Networks; OQPSK-DSSS; SUN-OFDM; interference.

1. Introduction

The IEEE 802.15.4 standard [1] was first released in May 2003 and defined a physical layer (PHY) and a MAC (Medium Access Control) layer for WPAN (Wireless Personal Area Networks) operating in the sub-GHz (868 MHz in Europe, 915 MHz in America) and the 2.4 GHz worldwide ISM (Industrial, Scientific and Medical) frequency bands [2]. The PHY layer was built upon the DSSS-OQPSK (Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum - Offset Quadrature Phase Shift Keying) modulation and provided data rates of 20 kbps and 40 kbps in the sub-GHz bands, respectively, and of 250 kbps in the 2.4 GHz band. At the MAC layer, the standard defined slotted/synchronized and unslotted/unsynchronized operation based on the CSMA/CA (Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance) channel access mechanism to trade off bandwidth, latency and energy consumption of the devices.

Thanks to its simplicity and low-cost, over the years the IEEE 802.15.4 standard has become the basis for multiple low-power wireless communications technologies including ZigBee [3], ISA100.11a [4], WirelessHART [5], 6TiSCH [6] and Thread [7], among others. In fact, the adoption of the IEEE 802.15.4 standard by different standardization bodies and technologies has promoted the revision of the standard (i.e. three times: in 2006, 2011 and 2015) in order to clarify the operation and to add new features to both the PHY and MAC layers. For example, the 2015 standard revision

30 adopted the MAC layer proposals defined in the IEEE 802.15.4e-2012 [8] amendment. Among others,
31 this amendment defined the TSCH (Time Slotted Channel Hopping), a channel access mechanism that
32 combines TDMA (Time Division Multiple Access) and FDMA (Frequency Division Multiple Access) to
33 support industrial requirements, including reliable packet delivery (i.e. 99.999%) in adverse conditions
34 such as multi-path propagation and external interference.

35 Similarly, the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 standard revision included three new physical layers targeted to
36 SUN (Smart Utility Network) applications [9], SUN-FSK, SUN-OQPSK and SUN-OFDM, as defined
37 in the IEEE 802.15.4g-2012 [10] amendment. The SUN-FSK and SUN-OQPSK modulations focus on
38 maintaining backwards compatibility with previous standards and commercially available transceivers,
39 whereas the SUN-OFDM is focused on adding robustness and improving spectrum efficiency at the
40 physical layer. The benefits brought by SUN-OFDM are mainly due to the use of parallel transmissions
41 with orthogonal sub-carriers, each transporting a small portion of the information to be transmitted
42 using a narrow-band modulation. Such approach provides better robustness against multi-path
43 propagation (as sub-channels can be considered flat fading, which are inherently robust to inter-symbol
44 and inter-frame interference) and external interference (as narrow-band interference only affects a
45 portion of the sub-channels and frequency repetition can be used to overcome its effects), as well as
46 improving spectrum efficiency (sub-channels are optimally spaced, allowing to trade-off robustness or
47 data-rate depending on the application requirements).

48 The consolidation of the IEEE 802.15.4g-2012 amendment into the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 standard, as
49 well as the appearance of the first commercially available radio transceivers supporting it, entails a
50 shift in the design, development and deployment of low-power wireless networks, with special interest
51 in the industrial domain, where the propagation and interference effects have largely slowed or limited
52 the adoption of such technologies. Taking that into account, in this paper we focus on empirically
53 evaluating the interference robustness of the SUN-OFDM and compare it against OQPSK-DSSS. Our
54 goal is to provide evidence of the robustness of the different modulations, including their possible
55 configurations and under different operating conditions, to understand the benefits and limitations
56 when deploying such technologies. To the best of our knowledge, these results are novel and help
57 researchers and practitioners deploy low-power wireless networks that are more robust and make an
58 efficient use of the spectrum in real-world scenarios.

59 The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview on the PHYs
60 defined in the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 standard that are evaluated in this article. Section 3 provides a survey
61 of the research related to the SUN-OFDM physical layer for low-power wireless networks. Section 4
62 presents the methodology and the setup used to conduct the experiments to evaluate the robustness
63 of the SUN-OFDM and OQPSK-DSSS PHYs. Section 5 presents and summarizes the results obtained
64 from the measurement campaign. Section 6 discusses the results obtained and presents a series of
65 recommendations. Finally, Section 7 concludes this article.

66 2. IEEE 802.15.4-2015 Overview

67 The 2015 version of the IEEE 802.15.4 standard offers 18 different physical layers, each targeting
68 specific applications and market segments. In this section, we present and briefly describe the two
69 physical layers analyzed in this paper, that is, OQPSK-DSSS and SUN-OFDM.

70 2.1. IEEE 802.15.4-2015 OQPSK-DSSS

71 OQPSK-DSSS was introduced in the original IEEE 802.15.4 standard in 2003.

72 OQPSK-DSSS uses 16-ary quasi-orthogonal modulation where each data symbol represents 4 bits
73 of information. Therefore, there are 16 possible symbols and each of them is represented by a PRNG
74 (Pseudo-Random Noise Generator) chip sequence that is an almost orthogonal.

75 When operating in the 780 MHz, 915 MHz, 2380 MHz and 2450 MHz bands, the PRN sequence is
76 32 chips long for 4 bits of data, hence providing a data rate of 250 kbps. In contrast, when operating in

77 the 868 MHz band, the PRN sequence is 16 chips long for 4 bits of data, thus offering a data rate of
78 100 kbps.

79 OQPSK-DSSS frames are composed of a SHR (Synchronization Header), PHR (PHY Header) and
80 PSDU (PHY Service Data Unit), as depicted in Fig. 1. The SHR contains a preamble and a SFD (Start of
81 Frame Delimiter); the PHR contains the frame length (7 bits) and a reserved bit. The maximum length
82 of the PSDU is 127 bytes.

83 OQPSK-DSSS used in the 2450 MHz band with 250 kbps data rate is the most common PHY
84 configuration deployed when this standard is used.

Figure 1. IEEE 802.15.4-2015 OQPSK-DSSS frame format.

85 2.2. IEEE 802.15.4 SUN-OFDM

86 The SUN-OFDM (Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing) physical layer was rolled into
87 the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 version of the standard alongside with SUN-FSK (Frequency Shift Keying)
88 and SUN-OQPSK (Offset Quadrature Phase Shift Keying). Whereas FSK and OQPSK are two
89 well-known modulation techniques that have been widely used in low-power wireless communications
90 thanks to its simplicity, performance and low-cost, OFDM has been commonly used in other
91 communication domains such as fixed and cellular access (e.g., xDSL, WiMAX, LTE), as well as
92 wired and wireless LANs (e.g., PLC, Wi-Fi) due to the stringent processing, memory and energy
93 consumption requirements.

94 The SUN-OFDM PHY can operate in both the sub-GHz bands (400, 700, 800 and 900 MHz) and
95 the 2.4 GHz (2400-2483.5 MHz) with data rates from 50 kbps to 800 kbps depending on the OFDM
96 option and MCS value, as summarized in Table 1.

97 As it can be observed, SUN-OFDM defines 4 options, numbered from 1 to 4, which determine
98 how many sub-carriers are grouped together in order to form an OFDM channel. Option 1, the largest,
99 groups 104 sub-carriers and occupies a bandwidth of 1094 kHz with 1200 kHz of channel spacing.
100 Option 4, the narrowest, groups 14 sub-carriers and occupies a bandwidth of 156 kHz with 200 kHz of
101 channel spacing. On top of that, the MCS (Modulation and Coding Scheme) parameter, numbered
102 from 0 to 6, determines how each sub-carrier is modulated (available modulation for each carrier are
103 BPSK, QPSK and 16-QAM), whether *frequency repetition* is applied (4x, 2x or no frequency repetition)
104 and the FEC (Forward Error Correction) rate applied to the input data stream for each sub-carrier
105 ($R = 1/2$ or $R = 3/4$).

106 Regardless of the OFDM option and MCS value, the sub-carrier spacing and symbol rate is
107 constant: $10416 \cdot 2/3$ Hz and $8 \cdot 1/3$ ksymbols/s. Each symbol in the OFDM physical layer is $120 \mu\text{s}$ long,
108 although the actual symbol transmission time is divided into a BS (Base Symbol) time of $96 \mu\text{s}$ and a
109 CP (Cyclic Prefix) time of $24 \mu\text{s}$. For each symbol, the CP is a replica of the last $1/4$ of the BS ($24 \mu\text{s}$)
110 and is copied at the front, making the signal periodic. The long duration of an OFDM symbol and
111 the fact that it is cyclic makes it robust against long spread time environments resulting in multi-path
112 propagation that may cause ISI (Inter-Symbol Interference) [11].

113 As per the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 standard, SUN-OFDM frames are composed of a SHR
114 (Synchronization Header), PHR (PHY Header) and PSDU (PHY Service Data Unit), as shown in
115 Fig. 2. The SHR is composed of a short and long preamble (STF and LTF, resp.), whereas the PHR
116 contains a header with the receiver configuration for the PHY payload (modulation and data rate,

Type	Mode	Modulation	Coding rate	Frequency repetition	Channel/Nominal bandwidth (kHz)	Total/Data/Pilot tones	Effective datarate (kbps)
OFDM1	MCS0	BPSK	1/2	4x	1200 / 1094	104/96/8	100
	MCS1	BPSK	1/2	2x			200
	MCS2	OQPSK	1/2	2x			400
	MCS3	OQPSK	1/2	0x			800
OFDM2	MCS0	BPSK	1/2	4x	800 / 552	52/48/4	50
	MCS1	BPSK	1/2	2x			100
	MCS2	OQPSK	1/2	2x			200
	MCS3	OQPSK	1/2	0x			400
	MCS4	OQPSK	3/4	0x			600
	MCS5	16-QAM	1/2	0x			800
OFDM3	MCS1	BPSK	1/2	2x	400 / 281	26/24/2	50
	MCS2	OQPSK	1/2	2x			100
	MCS3	OQPSK	1/2	0x			200
	MCS4	OQPSK	3/4	0x			300
	MCS5	16-QAM	1/2	0x			400
	MCS6	16-QAM	3/4	0x			600
OFDM4	MCS2	OQPSK	1/2	2x	200 / 156	14/12/2	50
	MCS3	OQPSK	1/2	0x			100
	MCS4	OQPSK	3/4	0x			150
	MCS5	16-QAM	1/2	0x			200
	MCS6	16-QAM	3/4	0x			300

Table 1. SUN-OFDM parameters.

117 frame length, scrambler configuration and a redundancy check). The OFDM header (SHR and PHR)
 118 is transmitted using the lowest supported MCS level for the OFDM option being used. That is,
 119 for OFDM1 and OFDM2 the header is transmitted using MCS0 (BPSK, $R=1/2$, 4x repetition); for
 120 OFDM3 the header is transmitted using MCS1 (BPSK, $R=1/2$, 2x repetition); for OFDM4 the header is
 121 transmitted using MCS2 (QPSK, $R=1/2$, 2x repetition). Therefore, for any device implementing any of
 122 the OFDM options, implementation of the BPSK and QPSK is mandatory and support of 16-QAM is
 123 optional. Finally, the maximum length of the PSDU is 2047 bytes, large enough to transport a complete
 124 IPv6 packet without fragmentation.

Figure 2. IEEE 802.15.4-2015 SUN-OFDM frame format.

125 3. Related Work

126 Despite being introduced in the IEEE 802.15.4g-2012 amendment, the SUN-OFDM PHY has not
 127 received a lot of attention from the research community to understand the potential benefits (and
 128 pitfalls) of applying this technology in low-power wireless communications for industrial applications.
 129 This is mainly due to the lack of commercially available radio transceivers that support all standard
 130 modes. In this section, we provide a summary of related work that has evaluated the performance of
 131 the PHYs proposed in the IEEE 802.15.4g-2012 amendment. The results are presented in chronological
 132 order.

133 In [12], the authors experimentally evaluate various LPWAN (Low-Power Wide-Area Network)
 134 technologies for industrial sensing applications, including condition monitoring. The results, which

135 include LoRa (Long Range) and IEEE 802.15.4g (using SUN-FSK only), conclude that with respect to
136 IEEE 802.15.4g (SUN-FSK), LoRa provides the largest communication range (2x) at the expense of an
137 increased energy consumption (10x).

138 In [13], the authors study the coexistence mechanisms of homogeneous and heterogeneous
139 IEEE 802.15.4g systems for SUN, and perform a coexistence analysis to evaluate the performance
140 degradation of a victim system in the presence of an interferer. They show that with a distance over
141 30 m the victim and the interferer are able to coexist even without any higher layer mechanism that
142 enforce coexistence.

143 In [14], the authors study the coexistence of IEEE 802.11ah and IEEE 802.15.4g networks, which
144 provide communication ranges above 1 km, and are specifically targeted at outdoor IoT (Internet of
145 Things) applications. Simulation results show that co-located IEEE 802.11ah networks can severely
146 impact the operation of IEEE 802.15.4g networks due to the higher ED (Energy Detection) threshold
147 and the faster back-off mechanism. Moreover, the differences in modulation scheme and frame
148 structure limit the capability to implement automatic mechanisms to enforce cooperation. Hence,
149 self-coexistence mechanism need to be enforced to mitigate the effects of interference in the network
150 performance.

151 More recently, in [15] and [16] the authors evaluate the suitability of the IEEE 802.15.4g-2012
152 physical layers for environmental and smart building applications respectively, showing that
153 SUN-OFDM is affected by multi-path fading and external interference in a similar way as OQPSK-DSSS.
154 Based on these results, in [17], the authors conclude that the SUN-OFDM physical layer alone does not
155 yield the robustness required for industrial applications and, thus, they recommend to add channel
156 hopping techniques to combat its effects.

157 4. Methodology and Setup

158 In this section, we present the research methodology that we have used to evaluate the interference
159 robustness of the SUN-OFDM modes and compare it with the OQPSK-DSSS mode, both defined in the
160 IEEE 802.15.4-2015 PHYs.

161 4.1. Evaluation Methodology

162 To evaluate the interference robustness of the SUN-OFDM PHY and compare it to the
163 OQPSK-DSSS PHY, we use the setup depicted in Fig. 3. The setup consists of a transmitter, a receiver
164 and an interferer device connected through an RF power combiner (further described in Section 4.3).

165 For the SUN-OFDM modulation, we select the operating modes that provide a similar data-rate
166 of the OQPSK-DSSS mode, 250 kbps. In particular, we select the OFDM1-MCS1, OFDM2-MCS2,
167 OFDM3-MCS3 and OFDM4-MCS5 modes that provide a data-rate of 200 kbps but with different PHY
168 properties (i.e. channel bandwidth, modulation, coding rate and frequency repetition) as presented in
169 Section 2 and summarized in Table 2.

170 For the measurement campaign, each selected modulation is used as an interferer signal,
171 and tested against all other selected modulations acting as transmitter signals (OFDM1-MCS1,
172 OFDM2-MCS2, OFDM3-MCS3, OFDM4-MCS5, OQPSK-DSSS). The procedure is also repeated for two
173 different payload lengths (20 bytes and 120 bytes) in order to understand the effects of packet length
174 on the robustness of each modulation. This is relevant as the SUN-OFDM modulation adds symbol
175 redundancy in both time and frequency, whereas OQPSK-DSSS only adds redundancy in terms of
176 the spreading factor gain. In addition, each base experiment is repeated twice for each transmitter
177 and interferer device (i.e. exchanging the devices' roles). We use this approach to verify the obtained
178 results and cancel out possible differences in the transmit power between the devices (due to the radio
179 transceiver construction variability and/or the impedance matching of the RF circuit) that may affect
180 the obtained results.

181 Overall, this gives a total of 10 base experiments, one for each interferer signal and payload length,
182 as presented in Section 5. Each base experiment uses a particular modulation as interferer, and tests

Figure 3. Evaluation setup. Note that the grey box around the transmitter, interferer and receiver devices represents a RF shielding enclosure used to ensure that communication between devices can only occur through the RF coaxial cables.

Name	Mode	Modulation	Channel coding	Frequency repetition	Receiver sensitivity (dBm)	Effective data-rate (kbps)	Channel bandwidth (kHz)	Abbreviation
OQPSK-DSSS	N/A	OQPSK	N/A	N/A	-103	250	5000	OQPSK-DSSS
OFDM Option 1	MCS1	BPSK	1/2	2x	-109	200	1200	OFDM1-MCS1
OFDM Option 2	MCS2	QPSK	1/2	2x	-108	200	800	OFDM2-MCS2
OFDM Option 3	MCS3	QPSK	1/2	0x	-107	200	400	OFDM3-MCS3
OFDM Option 4	MCS5	16-QAM	1/2	0x	-105	200	200	OFDM4-MCS5

Table 2. IEEE 802.15.4-2015 modulations that have been selected in this study to evaluate their robustness against interference.

183 the robustness of all the modulations being tested in the measurement campaign, including itself. For
 184 instance, OFDM1-MCS1 is selected as intereferer and tested against OFDM1-MCS1, OFDM2-MCS2,
 185 OFDM3-MCS3, OFDM4-MCS5 and OQPSK-DSSS.

186 To ensure that noise and external interference do not affect the results, we set the transmit power to
 187 a value that is well above the sensitivity limit of the radio transceiver for each modulation being tested,
 188 and conduct the experiments using RF coaxial cables while each board is enclosed in an individual
 189 Faraday cage. Second, when both transmitter and interferer devices use the same modulation, it is
 190 possible that the receiver synchronizes to the header transmitted by the interferer. To avoid this, the
 191 interferer device uses continuous transmit mode and starts transmitting 10 ms before the transmitter
 192 device starts sending data packets.

193 4.2. Base experiment

194 The independent variable of each base experiment is the SIR (Signal to Interference Ratio), defined
 195 as the ratio between the power of the transmitter signal and the power of the interferer signal; thermal
 196 noise is not taken into account since both signals are well-above its value ($P_N = -107$ dBm) considering
 197 the experiment conditions, i.e., ambient temperature ($T = 25^\circ\text{C}$) and signal bandwidth ($B \leq 5$ MHz).
 198 In contrast, the dependent variable of each experiment is the PDR (Packet Delivery Ratio), defined

199 as the percentage of packets that are successfully received at the receiver under the presence of the
200 interference signal generated by the interferer device.

201 For all the experiments, the value of the SIR ranges from -12 dB to +6 dB, meaning that the
202 transmitter power is between 1/16x and 4x the interferer power. We use such a wide SIR range
203 to ensure that the PDR transitions from 100% to 0% regardless of the interferer and transmitter
204 modulation under test. In addition, to validate the results obtained of each base experiment, the first
205 test is conducted without interference signal (the interferer device does not transmit during that test).
206 In that case, the PDR is expected to be 100%. This can be observed with the *Inf* mark in the x-axis of
207 the figures presented in Section 5.

208 To determine the PDR for each SIR for a given transmit modulation, the transmitter device sends
209 1000 frames to the receiver device. Frames are transmitted with a 5 ms inter-packet delay. The payload
210 is composed of the {0x00, 0x01, ..., 0x13} sequence for the 20-byte payload and the {0x00, 0x01, ..., 0x77}
211 sequence for the 120-byte payload. Each frame is completed with the FCS field of the PSDU depending
212 on the selected modulation (2 bytes for OQPSK-DSSS, 4 bytes for SUN-OFDM).

213 During the transmission, the interferer device injects an interfering signal using the selected
214 modulation for that particular base experiment. In contrast to data packets, the payload of the
215 interference packets is composed of a 123-byte {0x55, ..., 0x55} sequence. That payload is transmitted
216 continuously using the continuous transmission feature of the AT86RF215 radio transceiver. That is,
217 the transceiver operates in packet mode but the packet header (SHR + PHR) is only transmitted once
218 and the payload (PSDU + FCS) is transmitted indefinitely until the experiment is finished.

219 There are two conditions that need to be met for a packet to be considered successfully received.
220 First, the FCS calculated by the receiver radio transceiver based on the received bytes has to match the
221 FCS value attached by the transmitter device at the end of the payload. Second, the received bytes
222 have to match the transmitted bytes depending on the packet length for that base experiment. This
223 ensures that the PDR results are correct even in the unexpected case where the calculated FCS sequence
224 matches the received FCS sequence despite one or multiple bit errors caused by the interferer signal.

225 4.3. Setup

226 For the transmitter, receiver and interferer devices we use the OpenMote-B [18,19] shown in
227 Fig. 4. The OpenMote-B is equipped with a Texas Instruments CC2538 SoC (System on Chip) and a
228 Microchip AT86RF215 radio transceiver. The CC2538 [20] includes an ARM Cortex-M3 micro-controller
229 (32 MHz, 32 kB RAM, 512 kB Flash) and a radio transceiver compatible with the IEEE 802.15.4-2006
230 standard. The AT86RF215 [21] is a dual-band (sub-GHz and 2.4 GHz) radio transceiver compatible
231 with the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 standard, which supports all Multi-Rate PHY options defined in the
232 IEEE 802.15.4g-2012 amendment for Smart Utility Networks (SUN).

233 As depicted in Fig. 3, the boards are connected using an Agilent 87302C RF power combiner that
234 operates in the 0.5-26.5 GHz band and provides an input attenuation of 3 dB for the input channels
235 towards the output channel, and a return loss of 24 dB. The output of the RF power combiner is further
236 attenuated using a Minicircuits 30 dB RF attenuator to ensure that the received signal at the receiver
237 device is within the receive power limits of the AT86RF215 radio transceiver (-5 dBm according to the
238 data-sheet).

239 To coordinate the actions between the different devices, a computer running Ubuntu 18.04
240 LTS is used. The computer is connected to the OpenMote-B boards over USB, and executes
241 a Python script that orchestrates an experiment. For each board, the script uploads the radio
242 configuration to be used (i.e. modulation type, transmit power and packet length, among others)
243 and starts transmission/reception. The OpenMote-B boards execute a custom firmware that receives
244 commands over UART (Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter), execute the action commanded
245 (i.e. transmit a packet, start receiving, etc.) and return the result (i.e. packet successfully received or
246 not).

Figure 4. OpenMote-B board. The CC2538 (MCU) and the AT86RF215 (radio transceiver) are interconnected using the SPI bus, whereas the CC2538 (MCU) is connected to the computer using the USB-UART bridge (FTDI FT2232).

247 4.4. Radio Calibration

248 The PDR is evaluated with respect to SIR between the transmit power of the data and the interferer
 249 signals. According to the AT86RF215 radio transceiver datasheet (specifically Fig. 11-2), there is a 6 dB
 250 offset between the value of the transmit power configuration register (RFn_PAX.TXPWR) and the actual
 251 transmit power of the radio transceiver depending on the selected modulation (OQPSK-DSSS and
 252 SUN-OFDM).

253 Such difference in transmit power between different modulations can have an impact on the
 254 obtained results. For instance, an uncontrolled higher transmit power of the data signal results in a
 255 better PDR result for that particular modulation. Similarly, an uncontrolled lower transmit power of
 256 the interferer signal also results in a better PDR for that particular modulation. To validate the offset
 257 and obtain the configuration register values that ensure the same transmit power for both modulations,
 258 we calibrate using a Rigol DSA-815 spectrum analyzer as the Test Equipment (TE), and an OpenMote-B
 259 as the Device Under Test (DUT).

260 The DUT is connected to TE using a RF cable and the radio calibration procedure is performed as
 261 follows. For each modulation, the DUT is configured to transmit with a known power configuration
 262 register and the TE is configured to measure the power in the band taking into consideration the
 263 parameters of the modulation under test (i.e. center frequency, occupied bandwidth and span). The
 264 procedure is repeated for all the values of the power configuration register (from 0 to 30 with a 3 unit
 265 step) to obtain the relation between those values and the actual transmit powers that are generated by
 266 the radio transceiver, as shown in Table 3.

267 Overall, results are in accordance with the data provided in the datasheet and allow to empirically
 268 determine the transmit power configuration register values for the OQPSK-DSSS and the SUN-OFDM
 269 modulations. In particular, we have decided to use a transmit power between -9 dBm and +9 dBm,
 270 as these are the values that are common to both modulations. We then define the default transmit
 271 power of +3 dBm, and let the interferer power range from -9 dBm to +9 dBm, corresponding to the SIR
 272 between -12 dB and +6 dB described earlier.

273 5. Results

274 Results obtained using the research methodology and the experiment setup described in
 275 the previous section are presented for each interferer modulation (OFDM1-MCS1, OFDM2-MCS2,
 276 OFDM3-MCS3, OFDM4-MCS5 and OQPSK-DSSS) and packet length (20 bytes and 120 bytes) in Fig. 5,

RfN_PAX.TXPWR	Transmit power (dBm)				
	OQPSK-DSSS	OFDM1-MCS1	OFDM2-MCS2	OFDM3-MCS3	OFDM4-MCS54
30	15	9	9	9	9
27	14	8	8	8	8
24	12	5	5	5	5
21	9	2	2	2	2
18	6	-1	-1	-1	-1
15	3	-3	-3	-3	-3
12	0	-7	-7	-7	-7
9	-3	-11	-11	-11	-11
6	-6	-14	-14	-14	-14
3	-9	-16	-16	-16	-16
0	-12	-18	-18	-18	-18

Table 3. Transmit power values for the OQPSK-DSSS and the SUN-OFDM modulations. Notice that the results have been rounded to the closest dB given the resolution of the DUT and the uncertainty of the TE.

277 6, 7, 8 and 9, respectively. Table 4 summarizes the required SIR (dB) to ensure PDR > 80% for each
 278 modulation and packet length.

Figure 5. OFDM1-MCS1 interference results.

Figure 6. OFDM2-MCS2 interference results.

Figure 7. OFDM3-MCS3 interference results.

Figure 8. OFDM4-MCS5 interference results.

Figure 9. OQPSK-DSSS interference results.

279 For example, if we consider an interfering signal modulated using OFDM1-MCS1, we can observe
 280 that, for a 20 byte PSDU, the OFDM1-MCS1, OFDM2-MCS2 and OFDM-MCS3 physical layers perform
 281 similarly, requiring $SIR > 1$ dB for $PDR > 80\%$. OFDM4-MCS5 requires $SIR > 5$ dB to provide a $PDR > 80\%$.

	Interference type and packet length (bytes)									
	OFDM1-MCS1		OFDM2-MCS2		OFDM3-MCS3		OFDM4-MCS5		OQPSK-DSSS	
	20	120	20	120	20	120	20	120	20	120
OQDM1-MCS1	1	2	2	3	3	4	2	3	-1	-1
OQDM1-MCS2	2	4	5	6	5	6	5	7	-5	-3
OQDM3-MCS3	2	4	5	6	8	9	8	9	-5	-3
OQDM4-MCS5	5	7	8	10	10	12	>12	>12	-2	0
OQPSK-DSSS	8	12	8	12	8	12	9	12	6	8

Table 4. Results summary. Each value in the table is the required SIR (dB) to ensure a PDR > 80% for each modulation (OFDM1-MCS1, OFDM2-MCS2, OFDM3-MCS3, OFDM4-MCS5, OQPSK-DSSS) and packet length (20, 120 bytes).

282 In contrast, for a 120 B PSDU, OFDM1-MCS1 requires a SIR > 2 dB, OFDM2-MCS2 and OFDM3-MCS3
 283 require SIR > 4 dB, and OFDM4-MCS5 requires a SIR > 7 dB. Finally, for a 20 byte and 120 byte PSDU,
 284 OQPSK-DSSS requires a SIR > 8 dB and a SIR > 12 dB for PDR > 80%, resp.

285 These results show that OQPSK-DSSS requires 6 dB higher SIR to achieve PDR > 80% when
 286 compared to OFDM1-MCS1 under the same interference. Considering that OQPSK-DSSS uses a
 287 5 MHz channel bandwidth while OFDM1-MCS1 uses 1.2 MHz channel bandwidth, we can derive that
 288 OFDM provides increased spectral efficiency and robustness. Similar results can be derived for other
 289 combinations, as presented in Table 4.

290 Interestingly, considering an interfering signal modulated using OQPSK-DSSS, if we consider
 291 a system using OFDM1-MCS1 and we compare it to the same system using OQPSK-DSSS, we can
 292 observe that OFDM1-MCS1 can still operate with PDR > 80% even if the interference level is 1 dB above
 293 the signal level. This is particularly interesting because OQPSK-DSSS is widely used.

294 6. Discussion and Recommendations

295 This section discusses the results outlined in the previous section and presents recommendations
 296 to researchers and practitioners, serving as a tool to understand the behavior of each particular
 297 modulation under interference conditions, and motivating the use of the SUN-OFDM for deploying
 298 low-power wireless systems in industrial scenarios.

299 6.1. Discussion

300 Following we discuss the results presented in Table 4.

301 First, considering OFDM1-MCS1, we observe that a reduction in the bandwidth of the interference
 302 signal (i.e. going from OFDM2-MCS2 to OFDM4-MCS5 interference) requires a 2 dB SIR increase to
 303 provide a PDR > 80%. This can be attributed to the fact that the reduction in the bandwidth causes
 304 an increase in the PSD (Power Spectral Density) of the interference (i.e. a 3 dB increase each time the
 305 bandwidth is reduced by half) meaning that the probability of a symbol being corrupted increases.

306 Second, the SIR required for OFDM2-MCS2 and OFDM3-MCS3 is equivalent to OFDM1-MCS1
 307 and OFDM2-MCS2 regardless of packet size (2-4 dB and 5-6 dB, resp.). However, the effect of
 308 OFDM3-MCS3 interference causes a 3 dB SIR increase to the OFDM3-MCS3 signal (i.e. 7-8 dB) to
 309 maintain PDR > 80%, whereas the OFDM2-MCS2 signal remains unaffected (5-6 dB). Such results
 310 can be attributed to the fact that, despite both OFDM2-MCS2 and OFDM3-MCS3 using the same
 311 modulation (OQPSK with coding rate $R = 1/2$), the former takes advantage of the 2x frequency
 312 repetition providing an additional protection of 3 dB. The result is independent of packet length, which
 313 confirms the importance of using such protection mechanisms at the physical layer.

314 Third, the SIR required for OFDM4-MCS5 to maintain a PDR > 80% is higher compared to the
 315 other SUN-OFDM modulations and increases as the bandwidth of the interferer is reduced (going
 316 from OFDM1-MCS1 to OFDM4-MCS5 interference). This is an expected result, as the PSD of the
 317 interference increases by 3 dB every time the bandwidth is reduced by two, and taking into account that

318 OFDM4-MCS5 uses an aggressive modulation (16-QAM) in combination with a coding rate $R = 1/2$,
319 but does not employ time or frequency symbol repetition, leading to a higher BER (Bit Error Rate) in
320 the presence of interference.

321 Fourth, the SIR required for the OQPSK-DSSS modulation remains constant (8-12 dB depending
322 on packet length) regardless of the type of the SUN-OFDM interference and, hence, the occupied
323 bandwidth. In contrast, OQPSK-DSSS modulation requires a smaller SIR (6-8 dB depending on
324 packet length) when the interference is OQPSK-DSSS. This can be attributed to a combination of facts
325 including that SUN-OFDM interference is composed of multiple pilots spread over the channel and
326 has a higher PSD, as well as the fact that OQPSK-DSSS does not provide any additional mechanism to
327 enhance the robustness of the transmission against interference except for the processing gain of DSSS
328 ($10 \cdot \log_{10}(2M/250k) = 9$ dB).

329 Fifth, SUN-OFDM modulations are robust against OQPSK-DSSS interference, requiring negative
330 SIR values (SIR < 0 dB) to maintain a PDR > 80%. This is an expected result that can be attributed to
331 the fact that SUN-OFDM modulation is a combination of narrowband modulation, whereas the
332 OQPSK-DSSS is inherently wideband, i.e. it has a very low PSD. In fact, the results show that
333 OFDM2-MCS2 and OFDM3-MCS3 require the same SIR, which is lower than OFDM1-MCS1. This
334 can be explained given that OFDM2-MCS2 employs 2x frequency repetition whereas OFDM3-MCS3
335 occupies half the bandwidth (400 kHz vs. 800 kHz, resulting in a 3 dB PSD increase).

336 As a numeric example of the above, for OFDM2-MCS2 the PSD for a transmit power of 0 dBm
337 and a bandwidth of 800 kHz is -29.03 dBm/Hz. In contrast, for OFDM3-MCS3, the PSD for a transmit
338 power of 0 dBm and a bandwidth of 400 kHz is -26.02 dBm/Hz. Finally, OQPSK-DSSS interference
339 with a transmit power of 0 dBm and a bandwidth of 2 MHz has a PSD of -33.01 dBm/Hz. Notice that,
340 for an SIR=0 dB, OFDM2-MCS2 has SIR=4 dB ($-29.03 - -33.01 = 3.98$ dB) whereas OFDM3-MCS3
341 has SIR=7 dB ($-26.02 - 33.01 = 6.99$ dB). In conclusion, when dealing with wideband interference
342 (here, OQPSK-DSSS) using 2x repetition provides a theoretical 3 dB advantage, but that advantage is
343 overcome by the bandwidth reduction that provides a higher PSD.

344 Another interesting result comparing the performance of the SUN-OFDM and OQPSK-DSSS
345 physical layers against interference is that the degradation in terms of PDR caused by the increment
346 of the packet length (going from 20 bytes to 120 bytes) is not equal for both modulation types. For
347 SUN-OFDM, the SIR increase to maintain a PDR > 80% is bounded to 2 dB, whereas for OQPSK-DSSS
348 the SIR increase is larger than 3 dB. This is thanks to time and frequency diversity, which allows to
349 recover random errors caused by multi-path propagation and external interference.

350 The SIR spread between operating in ideal conditions (PDR > 80%) and degraded conditions
351 (PDR < 20%) for all SUN-OFDM modulations requires SIR=3 dB regardless of the packet length.
352 In contrast, the SIR spread between operating in ideal conditions and degraded conditions for
353 OQPSK-DSSS depends on packet size and interference type. When dealing with SUN-OFDM
354 interference, transitions requires SIR=2 dB for 20-byte packets, and SIR=5 dB for 120-byte packets. In
355 contrast, when dealing with OQPSK-DSSS interference, the transition requires SIR=2 dB regardless of
356 packet length.

357 Comparing OFDM1-MCS1 to OQPSK-DSSS, we observe that for a PDR > 80%, it provides an
358 advantage between 5-10 dB, depending on interference type and packet length. In particular, it
359 provides an advantage of 5 dB for OFDM3-MCS3 interference with packet length of 20 bytes,
360 and an advantage of 10 dB for OFDM1-MCS1 interference with packet length of 120 bytes. This
361 is in contrast with the fact that OFDM1-MCS1 uses a channel separation of 1.2 MHz, whereas
362 OQPSK-DSSS uses a channel separation of 5 MHz. That is, the spectral efficiency of OFDM1-MCS1 is
363 0.166 bits/Hz (or 200 kbps/1200 kHz) whereas the spectral efficiency of OQPSK-DSSS is 0.05 bits/Hz
364 (or 250 kbps/5000 kHz). Hence, OFDM1-MCS1 provides an increased robustness level while offering
365 a higher spectral efficiency that enables to have denser deployments (a 333% capacity increase).

366 From these results, we can observe that the SIR required to provide PDR > 80% for OQPSK-DSSS
367 largely depends on the packet length (4 dB difference). In contrast, the SIR required to provide a

368 PDR > 80% for the robust SUN-OFDM modulations remains constant (< 1 dB) regardless of the packet
369 length and the interference type. This is owing to the fact that OQPSK-DSSS does not use any physical
370 layer mechanism to enhance robustness except for the processing gain provided by DSSS. Hence, the
371 error probability increases as the packet length is increased. For SUN-OFDM-based modulations, time
372 and frequency symbol repetition reduces the probability of having an erroneous bit.

373 6.2. Recommendations

374 Based on the results and the discussion presented above, we provide the following insights and
375 recommendations to researchers and practitioners deploying low-power wireless communication
376 systems using the SUN-OFDM physical layer in real-world environments:

- 377 1. Thanks to the small effect of packet length in the PDR with respect to the SIR, SUN-OFDM allows
378 to use larger packets (i.e. packet bundling) to increase the transmission efficiency (i.e. more
379 effective data with the same packet headers) without sacrificing robustness. In fact, SUN-OFDM
380 allows payloads of up to 2047 bytes, effectively allowing to transmit full IPv6 packets without
381 fragmentation or allowing to group up to sixteen 127-byte frames in a single 2047-byte frame.
- 382 2. Despite the fact that SUN-OFDM transceivers consume a higher amount of energy compared
383 to state-of-the-art IEEE 802.15.4 transceivers due to the additional circuitry required to operate
384 (scrambler, convolutional encoder, puncturer, interleaver, Viterbi decoder), the higher level of
385 robustness against interference provided by SUN-OFDM allows to use higher data rates (up to
386 800 kbps) to reduce the average energy consumption of the transmitter and the receiver devices.
- 387 3. As the preamble of a SUN-OFDM packet is transmitted using the lowest MCS option of the
388 current configuration, and includes information regarding the MCS option used to transmit the
389 packet payload, this allows the transmitter to switch between different MCS options of the same
390 SUN-OFDM configuration without any changes in the receiver configuration. It is hence possible
391 for the transmitter to use an aggressive modulation for an initial packet transmission, and use
392 a more robust modulation when re-transmitting. Similarly, acknowledgement frames can be
393 transmitted using the most robust modulation to increase the probability they are received.
- 394 4. Use of SUN-OFDM for deployments with a high device density and/or high interference
395 levels is advisable, as it provides higher spectral efficiency, while maintaining a similar level
396 of robustness against interference with respect to OQPSK-DSSS. If interference is of concern,
397 choosing OFDM1-MCS1 over OQPSK-DSSS translates into a 4x capacity increase while providing
398 an average advantage of 9 dB against the same interference. In contrast, if interference is not a
399 concern, choosing OFDM4-MCS5 offers a 26x capacity increase, while maintaining a similar level
400 of protection against the same type of interference.

401 7. Conclusions

402 This article evaluates the interference robustness of the OQPSK-DSSS and the SUN-OFDM
403 physical layers defined in the IEEE 802.15.4-2015 standard. Interfering conditions are generated in a
404 controlled setup to evaluate the SIR required by each modulation to achieve PDR > 80%. Compared to
405 OQPSK-DSSS, results show that SUN-OFDM provides at least 6 dB additional protection regardless
406 of interference type and packet length. In addition, SUN-OFDM only occupies 1.2 MHz bandwidth,
407 whereas OQPSK-DSSS occupies 5 MHz. This results in a higher spectral efficiency that allows one to
408 have denser deployments or to trade bandwidth efficiency and interference robustness depending on
409 the application requirements. Overall, the presented results become a useful tool to understand the
410 behavior of each particular modulation under interference conditions, and motivates the use of the
411 SUN-OFDM physical layer to deploy low-power wireless systems in industrial scenarios.

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420 Abbreviations

421 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

BPSK	Binary Phase Shift Keying
CSMA/CA	Carrier Sense Multiple Access / Collision Avoidance
DSSS	Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum
DUT	Device Under Test
ED	Energy Detection
FCS	Frame Check Sequence
FDMA	Frequency Division Multiple Access
FSK	Frequency Shift Keying
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers
ISM	Industrial, Scientific and Medical
LoRa	Long Range
LP-WAN	Low-Power Wide-Area Network
MAC	Medium Access Control
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MCU	Micro-Controller Unit
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
OQPSK	Offset Quadrature Phase-Shift Keying
422 PDR	Packet Delivery Ratio
PHR	PHY Header
PHY	Physical Layer
PRNG	Pseudo-Random Noise Generator
PSD	Power Spectral Density
PSDU	PHY Service Data Unit
QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
QPSK	Quadrature Phase Shift Keying
SFD	Start-of-Frame Delimiter
SHR	Synchronization Header
SIR	Signal-to-Interference Ratio
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interface
SUN	Smart Utility Networks
TDMA	Time Division Multiple Access
TE	Test Equipment
TSCH	Time Slotted Channel Hopping
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter
USB	Universal Serial Bus

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